

AWARENESS LEVEL OF FARMERS REGARDING THE PREVAILING ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES IN SOUTH GUJARAT REGION

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Abstract

Environmental issues encompass a broad spectrum of challenges arising from human activities and natural processes that exert detrimental effects on the natural environment and its ecosystems. Environmental change is impacting the natural ecosystem and is expected to have substantial adverse effect, mainly on agriculture which is the major occupation and livelihood of 52.00 per cent of population. Around 60 per cent cultivated land under soil erosion, water logging and salinity it significantly reduce the properties of soil and crop yield and ground water level was decline by 61 percent between 2007-2017. The study was conducted in seven district of South Gujarat. Two taluka were selected from each district and five villages from each selected taluks. Five farmers were selected randomly from each selected villages. Thus, total 350 farmers selected for present investigation. Farmers had high to medium level of awareness about environmental issues. Majority of farmers were aware about change in rainfall pattern and soil fertility are decreased in past 10 year.

Key word: environmental issues, agriculture, awareness and farmers

Introduction

Environmental issues encompass a broad spectrum of challenges arising from human activities and natural processes that exert detrimental effects on the natural environment and its ecosystems. These issues encompass various aspects, including but not limited to climate change, biodiversity loss, deforestation, pollution (air, water, and soil), habitat degradation, resource depletion, and unsustainable land use practices. The complex interplay of these environmental issues poses significant threats to the stability and resilience of ecosystems, as well as to human well-being and socio-economic systems. The intricate relationship between environmental issues and agriculture lies at the crux of sustainable development challenges. Agriculture, as a vital sector for global food security and livelihoods, profoundly impacts the environment. The intensification of agricultural practices, land-use changes, and agrochemical usage exert considerable pressures on ecosystems, leading to issues such as soil degradation, water pollution, loss of biodiversity, greenhouse gas emissions, and climate change. Concurrently, environmental changes, such as altered weather patterns and temperature fluctuations, directly influence agricultural productivity and crop suitability.

The key environmental challenges in India were significant in the past two decades. Climate change is impacting the natural ecosystem and is expected to have substantial adverse effect, mainly on agriculture which is the major occupation and livelihood of 52.00 per cent of population. Environmental change will also cause increased frequency of extreme events such as floods, drought, pest and disease attack, soil erosion and infertility etc. It is estimated that 97.85 million ha area of country is undergoing land degradation. i.e. 29.77% of the total geographical area of the country during 2018-19. In Gujarat. around 52.22% of total geographical area is undergoing land degradation during 2018-19. Around 60 per cent cultivated land under soil erosion, water logging and salinity it significantly reduce the properties of soil and crop yield and ground water level was decline by 61 percent between 2007-2017 (GOI, 2021). Based on some of the past experiences indicated above, impact of climate change on agriculture will be one of the major deciding factors influencing the future food security of mankind on the earth. Addressing and mitigating these issues requires interdisciplinary approaches, innovative solutions, and concerted efforts from

individuals, communities, policymakers, and scientific communities to ensure a sustainable and habitable planet for future generations.

An in-depth analysis of farmers' environmental awareness and the determinants influencing their awareness levels is essential for formulating effective policies and programs to foster successful awareness among farmers and address environmental issues. This investigation focused on farmers in South Gujarat, involved in the cultivation of agricultural and horticultural crops. The region exhibits a diverse ecosystem, comprising coastal, hilly, and green belt areas, making it susceptible to environmental changes, hence warranting the study's significance.

Objective

To study the awareness and perception of the respondents on the prevailing environmental issues

Research Methodology

An Ex-Post-Facto research design, which explores causal relationships after the occurrence of the phenomenon under investigation, was employed for this study due to its ongoing nature. The research was carried out in seven districts located in South Gujarat. In order to ensure a diverse representation of topography and climatic conditions, two talukas were purposively selected from each district, encompassing varied ecosystems such as coastal areas, hilly regions, and green belts. Additionally, five villages were chosen from each selected taluka. To gather data, a random sampling approach was utilized to select five farmers from each of the selected villages, resulting in a total of 350 participants for the present investigation.

The study employed a primary data collection approach, which involved gathering information directly from the sample respondents through the utilization of an interview schedule. The data was analyzed by using percentage, frequency, mean, standard deviation etc. to draw conclusion.

Result And Discussion**Awareness on Prevailing Environmental Issues**

Awareness refers to consciousness of farmers about prevailing environmental issues. The awareness taken more, as a cognitive behaviour has been operational as the farmer's consciousness, i.e. being fully aware, partial aware or not aware about prevailing environmental issues. The data were grouped into three categories viz., (i) low level of awareness (0 to 12 score), (ii) medium level of awareness (13 to 24 score) and (iii) high level of awareness (25 to 36 score) The data of respondents' awareness regarding prevailing environmental issues are presented in table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of farmers according to their awareness on prevailing environmental issues

Sr.	Categories	Coastal belt (n=100)	Green belt (n=125)	Hilly belt (n=125)	Total (n=350)
		f / (%)	f / (%)	f / (%)	f / (%)
1	Low awareness	06 (6.00)	01 (0.80)	17 (13.60)	24 (6.85)
2	Medium awareness	26	38	60	124

		(26.00)	(30.40)	(48.00)	(35.43)
3	High awareness	68 (68.00)	86 (68.80)	48 (38.40)	202 (57.72)
	Total	100 (100.00)	125 (100.00)	125 (100.00)	350 (100.00)

From the data presented in above mentioned table, it can be seen that in coastal area, majority (68.00%) of the farmers had high level of awareness about prevailing environmental issues, followed by 26.00 and 6.00 per cent of them had medium and lower level of awareness, respectively. In case of green belt area, majority (68.80%) of the farmers had high level of environmental issues related awareness, followed by 30.40 and 0.80 per cent had medium and low level of awareness, respectively. While in case of hilly area, nearly half (48.00%) of the farmers had medium level of awareness about prevailing environmental issues, followed by 38.40 and 13.60 per cent of them had high and low level of awareness, respectively.

From above table it can also be observed that slightly less than three-fifth (57.72%) of total farmers were having with high level of awareness about prevailing environmental issues, followed by 35.43 per cent had medium and 6.85 per cent had low level of awareness about prevailing environmental issues. The probable reason behind this result might be that they are directly dependent on the environment for their livelihoods and more number of farmers had medium to high level of environmental concern and eco-friendly behaviour.

Statement Wise Awareness of the Farmers About Prevailing Environmental Issues

From below mentioned table 2 of statement wise awareness of farmers about prevailing environmental issues, it was observed that majority of the farmers were aware about change in rain fall pattern

with mean score 1.74 and it got rank 1st, followed by experience of decrease in soil fertility status in past 10 year (1.73 mean score and 2nd rank), awareness about the present environmental issues (1.69 mean score and 3rd rank), present degraded environmental situation due to human greed (1.65 mean score and 4th rank) and realization of the change in climate with passing years with 1.60 mean score and 5th rank.

Most of the farmers were also having with awareness about disappearance of local/traditional crop varieties and plants around themselves with 1.59 mean score and 6th rank as per the rank wise classification of awareness, followed by awareness about deteriorating soil health due to intensive agricultural practices as well as frequent insect pest attack due to climatic changes with mean score 1.58 and 7th rank, experience of adverse effect of environment change on human health with mean score 1.56 and 8th rank, experience of shift in cropping pattern due to climate change with mean score 1.55 and 9th rank, awareness about sea water intrusion with 1.31 mean score and 10th rank, awareness about depletion of groundwater table with mean score 1.18 and 11th rank and experience of increase in incidences of soil erosion with 1.13 mean score and 12th rank.

Less awareness was observed for some statements viz., change in food habit due to climatic change, followed by increment in temperature with passing years, experience of man-animal conflict, decrease in beneficial soil microbes, change in dressing pattern with mean scores 1.12, 1.14, 1.07, 1.00 and 0.85, respectively. These statements got rank from 13th to 17th, respectively.

Table 2: Statement wise awareness of the respondents about prevailing environmental issues

Sr.	Statement	Mean Score	Rank
1.	Are you aware about the present environmental issues?	1.69	3 rd
2.	Have you realized the change in climate with passing years?	1.60	5 th
3.	Have you noticed the change in rainfall pattern?	1.74	1 st
4.	Have you experienced the increment in temperature with every passing year?	1.10	14 th
5.	Have you experienced soil fertility are decreased in past 10 year?	1.73	2 nd
6.	Do the incidences of soil erosion have increased?	1.13	12 th
7.	Is there any decrease in the beneficial soil microbes?	1.00	16 th
8.	Are you aware about depletion of groundwater table?	1.18	11 th
9.	Do you know about sea water intrusion?	1.31	10 th
10.	Are you experiencing man-animal conflict?	1.07	15 th
11.	Do you accept that human greed has lead to present degraded environmental situation?	1.65	4 th
12.	Have you realized the deteriorating soil health due to intensive agricultural practices?	1.58	7 th
13.	Have you noticed about disappearance of local/traditional crop varieties and plants around you?	1.59	6 th
14.	Do climate changes have triggered frequent insect pest attack?	1.58	7 th
15.	Have you experienced a shift in cropping pattern due to climate change?	1.55	9 th
16.	Do you feel climate change has altered the dressing pattern?	0.85	17 th
17.	Does your food habits are changing with climate change?	1.12	13 th
18.	Have you experienced adverse effect of environment change on human health?	1.56	8 th

Conclusion

From present study concluded that farmers had high to medium level of awareness about environmental issues. However, there is a clear need to enhance awareness among farmers, as doing so could

facilitate an increase in their capacity to adopt and implement strategies aimed at mitigating the environmental issues. Additionally, it is imperative to promote sustainable practices and enhance the

capabilities of extension services in order to assist farmers in the development and adoption of suitable sustainable practices.

Policy Implication

It is imperative to reinforce and fortify the extension service to augment farmers' comprehension of environmental issues and equip them with knowledge and skills pertaining to adaptive measures. Additionally, there is a need to advocate and promote the adoption of appropriate and indigenous technologies that align with the local context, enabling farmers to effectively adapt to the challenges posed by the changing environment.

The strategic implementation of extension services guided by region-specific agroecological knowledge and techniques is poised to foster a transition towards a more sustainable agricultural paradigm.

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